

Memorandum of Understanding Multi-Organizational Governance and Resourcing for the Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office

Preamble

The **Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office** is a collaborative project between Publishers International Linking Association, Inc. (PILA) dba Crossref (EIN 04-3502255), 50 Salem Street, Lynnfield 01940, MA, United States of America, Leiden University (KvK 27368929), more specifically the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), Kolffpad 1, 2333 BV Leiden The Netherlands and the FUNDACIÓ SIRIS - SIRIS FOUNDATION (NIF G44885416), Avgda Francesc Cambó, Num 17, 08003 Barcelona Spain (referred to as the “**Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office Operating Organizations**”). Serving as the cornerstone of project management for the Barcelona Declaration initiative, the Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office ensures the implementation of the Barcelona Declaration initiative’s efficiency, management, communication and overall success. The project has a duration of 3 years, at the end of which it will be automatically terminated, unless otherwise agreed.

The Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office Operating Organizations collectively assume and share responsibility for Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office operations and resourcing. These responsibilities are defined in this Memorandum of Understanding (MOU).

Definition of terms

- **Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office (BDOffice):** A three-year collaborative project providing management and operational support for the Barcelona Declaration initiative.
- **BDOffice Operating Organizations:** Crossref, Leiden University, more specifically the Centre for Science and Technology Studies, CWTS, and the SIRIS FOUNDATION.
- **BDOffice Steering Group:** A group comprising representatives from the Operating Organizations, responsible for overseeing resource allocation and facilitating the operations of the BDOffice.
- **Barcelona Declaration Board:** The governing body overseeing the strategic direction and governance of the Barcelona Declaration initiative.
- **BDOffice Team:** The staff responsible for executing the day-to-day operations and activities under the BDOffice.
- **BDOffice Executive Director:** The leader of the BDOffice, responsible for its overall management and strategic coordination.

- **BDOoffice Accounting Team:** The team responsible for handling the BDOoffice's day-to-day financial operations, including bookkeeping and accounts payable/receivable functions.
- **Barcelona Declaration initiative:** the initiative, prepared by a group of over 25 research information experts, representing organizations that carry out, fund, and evaluate research, as well as organizations that provide research information infrastructures to take the lead in transforming the way research information is used and produced with openness being the new norm.
- **Roadmap:** the outcome of The Paris Conference on Open Research Information September 2024 in the form of a concrete roadmap for coordinated activities.
- **Working group:** a working group involved in actually taking forward the actions listed in the roadmap.

Key tasks and functionalities of the Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office include:

- Facilitating and assisting the Working groups of the Roadmap: Providing organizational and logistical support to streamline group activities and ensure progress aligns with the initiative's goals.
- Supporting the preparation of meetings and reporting: Organizing agendas, preparing documentation, and producing reports to maintain transparency and effective communication among stakeholders.
- Managing the website and social media platforms: Overseeing online presence and communication channels to keep stakeholders informed and engaged.
- Promoting and engaging with the Barcelona Declaration: Leading dissemination efforts and fostering active participation from the community to expand the initiative's reach and impact.

Agreement

1. Purpose

This Memorandum of Understanding (MOU), dated as of January 1st 2025, constitutes a mutual understanding for collaboration between Crossref, CWTS Leiden, and the SIRIS Foundation. This MOA is a non-binding document whose purpose is to outline the parties' collective intent and commitments with respect to the sharing of respective roles and responsibilities of each party.

2. General Responsibilities and Duties:

Crossref, CWTS Leiden, and the SIRIS Foundation jointly oversee the economic support of the Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office (**BDOoffice**). Their responsibilities encompass governance, resource allocation, and the overall operational management of the office.

Each organization will contribute by financial support to the BDOffice, as outlined in an annual financial plan.

3. Governance Model:

Each of the BDOffice Operating Organizations appoints a representative to ensure adherence to this MOU. These representatives collectively form the **Steering Group**, a support body responsible for providing resources and facilitating the operations of the BDOffice. Decision-making authority and strategic direction for the Barcelona Declaration Initiative, and consequently for the activities of the BDOffice, will ultimately rest with the **Barcelona Declaration Board**, to be established in the first half of 2025.

Until the establishment of the Barcelona Declaration Board, the Steering Group will temporarily assume responsibility for the BDOffice's strategic guidelines. During this interim phase, the Steering Group will also include one representative from the organizations that coordinated the launch of the Barcelona Declaration¹. Once the Barcelona Declaration Board is in place, the Steering Group will transition to a facilitation-focused role, consisting solely of representatives from the BDOffice Operating Organizations.

4. Resourcing Model:

The BDOffice Operating Organizations are committed to the **3 years funding** of BDOffice's core operations. BDOffice's staffing and general operating expenses will be resourced and provided by the BDOffice Operating Organizations. Funding levels will be unanimously and with an equal contribution from each BDOffice Operating Organizations agreed by the BDOffice Steering Group as part of an annual budgeting process. Additional funding that BDOffice receives from grants, community contributions, or other sources may be used to offset the contributions of the Operating Organizations or to fund specific activities, specifically dedicated to organizing events, advocacy and communication actions.

5. Staffing:

The BDOffice will be staffed (BDOffice Team) with resources provided by the BDOffice Operating Organizations. At a minimum, the BDOffice will include an Executive Director and a Community Facilitation Manager. Additional roles may be added as necessary, contingent upon the availability of resources.

The BDOffice Team will focus on ensuring that the goals defined initially by the Steering Group and, once established, by the Barcelona Declaration Board are achieved effectively. At the end of the three-year period, the BDOffice Team will be dissolved, and staff hired explicitly for the project will cease their activities, unless future revisions or specific agreements are made regarding its continuation.

¹ Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative (COKI), Sorbonne University, and Sesame Open Science

6. Non-Personnel Expenses:

General non-personnel operating expenses will be resourced through the BDOoffice Operating Organizations as part of the annual budget.

7. Financial Administration:

Day-to-day bookkeeping and accounts payable/receivable functions will be administered by the Crossref accounting team.

- Crossref will be responsible for holding all shared BDOoffice funds in a designated bank account.
- Crossref finance team will ensure that all transactions are processed and tracked in a way that allows the Executive Director to have full transparency.
- Based on the annual budget provided by the Operating Organizations, the Executive Director will prepare and propose a yearly budget for approval by the Steering Group. Once the yearly budget is approved, the Executive Director will have the autonomy to manage expenses in accordance with the annual budget.
- Decisions regarding salary payments will require unanimous written approval from the BDOoffice Steering Group.
- The Executive Director will share financial reports with the Steering Group on a regular basis (6 months).
- Funds will be accounted for and will be reflected in Crossref financial statements.
- Crossref assumes the responsibility for the auditing of BDOoffice funds as part of its annual audit.

8. MOU Review:

This Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) is valid until 31 December 2027 (3 years) but will be reviewed annually. It may also be reviewed and modified at any time, as deemed appropriate, with the written consent of all Operating Organizations.

9. Termination of Agreement:

A governing organization intending to withdraw from this agreement must provide six months' written notice to the BDOoffice Steering Group. Following this notice, the remaining BDOoffice Operating Organization(s) will have 90 days to decide on the next steps, including whether to replace the departing organization(s). If a replacement organization is selected, it must meet the General Responsibilities and Duties outlined in this agreement and adhere to the Governance Model.

All BDOoffice Operating Organizations will collaborate to ensure a smooth transition to a new model, prioritizing the sustainability of the BDOoffice. In the event the agreement is terminated entirely, with all Operating Organizations opting to exit, they will work together to facilitate an orderly transition, ensuring the continuation of the BDOoffice operations until the conclusion of the three-year project period.

**Signed for and on behalf of the Barcelona Declaration Project Management Office
Operating Organizations as follows:**

Crossref

Name: Ginny Hendricks

Place: London, UK

Date: 15th January 2025

Signature

SIRIS Foundation

Name: Bernardo Rondelli

Place: Barcelona, Spain

Date: 15th January 2025_

Signature

Leiden University

Name: Prof.dr. B.A. Barendregt

Place: Leiden, The Netherlands

Date: 15th January 2025

Signature

